

Structural Changes of C₆₀, C₇₀ Mixture Fullerite at Heating by the Action of Pulsed Laser Beam

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Abstract Structural transformations take place in the near-surface layer during the recording of fullerene mass spectrum under the action of laser beam. The changes are associated with the sequential degradation of fullerite on the scheme: crystallites →fullerenes→carbon clusters, soot.

Keywords fullerite surface temperature, degradation fullerite crystallites, sublimation enthalpy of fullerenes, atomization of fullerenes

Introduction

Literature discusses not infrequently questions on the nature of variability of fullerene mass spectrum.

This paper deals with the study of transformations taking place on the fullerite surface during the recording of the fullerene mass spectrum with negative charge under the action of laser beam.

The aim of the work is to determine the nature of structural changes of fullerite on heating by the action of laser beam.

Materials and Methods

The mass spectrum of a fullerene sample synthesized at an arc current of 100 A with the helium flow rate $q = 2 \text{ cm}^3/\text{s}$ at the pressure $p \approx 0.11 \text{ MPa}$ was analyzed.

Figure 1: Mass spectrum of fullerene ions with negative charge, which was obtained at the laser beam parameters: pulse energy $q = 3.5 \mu\text{J}$, $f = 5 \text{ s}^{-1}$, $\tau^* = 30 \text{ ns}$ is accelerating voltage delay at the radiation power density $W = 0.12 \text{ MW/cm}^2$ [1].

Fullerenes were extracted from carbon black in benzene; the fullerite samples were prepared on an Al-plate substrate. The mass spectra have been obtained on the AutoFlex time-of-flight mass spectrometer (Bruker, Germany) with N₂ laser ($\lambda = 337$ nm) with the laser pulse duration $\tau_0 = 3$ ns. The optimal laser beam power level for recording fullerene mass spectrum was selected experimentally. In preliminary experiments it has been found that at the power density $W_0 \approx 0.1$ MW/cm², the background structures have a level of up to 5% of the C₆₀ peak value. Figure 1 shows an example of this mass spectrum [1].

To determine the fullerite surface temperature, a formula from Ref [2] was employed. It shows that in the case of the fullerite sublimation of the mixture containing C₆₀ and C₇₀ the surface temperature is:

$$T = 1032 / [0,35 + \lg(I_{60}/I_{70})], \quad (1)$$

where I_{60} / I_{70} is the ratio of the C₆₀ and C₇₀ peaks in the mass spectrum. The calculation of the data Fig 1 from Eq (1) gives the fullerite surface temperature $T \approx 1400$ K, which is much higher than the fullerene dimerization temperature [3, 4].

Figure 2 shows the peaks of C₆₀, C₇₀ and C₆₀O nanostructures, taken from 13 sequentially obtained mass spectra, which were recorded at a single point of a fullerite sample at the laser beam parameters presented in Fig 1.

Figure 2: Dependence of the peak values of the fullerenes C₆₀ (curve 1), C₇₀ (curve 2) and C₆₀O (curve 3) on the number N of laser pulses [1].

Results & Methods

A calculation from the points of the curves 1 and 2 of the mass spectrum in Fig 2 showed that the sample surface temperature decreases from 1400 K after the first packet of 20 pulses. Then under the action of pulses, the calculated surface temperature is 1100, 1000, ..., 800 K and lower.

It is seen from Fig 2 that the curves 1 and 2 are similar in shape: the peaks of the lines decrease with increasing number of laser pulses. The curves 1 and 2 consist of two parts. The initial steepest part corresponds to desorption with the lowest energy threshold. This is degradation of mixture fullerite crystallites. For C₆₀ and C₇₀, the sublimation enthalpy of crystallites $q_1 = 1.88 \times (1 \pm 0.02)$ eV and $q_2 = 2.0 \times (1 \pm 0.02)$ eV respectively [5]. Then the curves 1 and 2 (Fig 2) are changed into the second part of curves. Under the action of the same laser pulses are obtained the flat part. In this part, the sublimation rate is determined by the process with the highest threshold. That is fullerene degradation. The atomization energy of the fullerenes C₆₀ and C₇₀ there are $q_1^* = 7.4$ eV and $q_2^* = 8.1$ eV respectively [5].

The curve 3 in Fig. 2 shows that under ordinary synthesis and storage conditions, C₆₀O oxide is formed mainly on the fullerite surface, and that only a small part of it is contained in the thin near-surface layer.

The portion of sample treated with laser beam assumes a dark brown hue after mass spectrometry, a thin film of soot is discernible. This shows that fullerenes undergo a phase transition to a more stable phase. That is amorphous

constituent (graphite) under the action of laser beam energy. Fragments of fullerenes are partially ionized by laser beam and form a mass spectrum background, which is discernible in Fig 1 on the left of the C_{60} peak ($m/z = 720.617$ u). The remaining part of the fragments of fullerenes screens the irradiated surface, reduces the effective surface area of the sample and forms the flat part of the curves 1 and 2.

The above-mentioned surface temperature decrease is associated with degradation processes of crystallites and fullerenes. Indeed, since the initial crystallites were formed on the substrate by the action of Van der Waals bulk forces in the case of solvent removal, crystallites are compacted towards the Al-plate substrates by the action of laser pulses and sublimation. In this case, thermal contact improves, and the sample temperature and peak values decrease also.

The quantitative assessment of the model of the process question from the curves 1 and 2 (Fig 2) was performed by calculation. The experimental value of the slope of the curve in for the C_n cluster was determined from the relation: $F_n = \Delta A_n / \Delta t_n$, where ΔA_n is change in the spectrum peak value of a particular cluster within the time interval Δt_n = $k \times \Delta N_n$, where k is a coefficient, and ΔN_n is the number of pulses within the given time interval Δt_n . The ratio of the slope values of the first and second part (M_n) is determined from the relation: $M_n = F_{n1} / F_{n2}$, where F_{n1} , F_{n2} are the slope values of the first and second part respectively. The experimental values of relative decrease in slope in Fig 2 are:

$$\text{Curve 1 for the fullerene } C_{60} : M_{60} = F_{60,1} / F_{60,2} = 37 \quad (2)$$

$$\text{Curve 2 for the fullerene } C_{70} : M_{70} = F_{70,1} / F_{70,2} = 51 \quad (3)$$

The values of (2) and (3) also correspond to the ratio of the threshold values of particular structures. In this case, we have for the fullerite C_{60} : $q_1^* / q_1 = 3.94$ and for the fullerite C_{70} : $q_2^* / q_2 = 4.05$.

Thus, the slope values of the curves 1 and 2, calculated from the experimental curves in Fig 2 using Eqs (2) and (3), agree with the value that determines the ratio of known threshold crystallite/cluster degradation values of fullerenes C_{60} and C_{70} .

Conclusion

- Transformations coming at a surface of fullerite under the action of the laser beam are tied with structural changes of material and conditions of closely fitting to substratum.
- After moving off remains of solution and demolishing crystal of C_{60} , C_{70} mix material is concentrated to substratum then goes lowering of material temperature.

Acknowledgment

Author is obliged to O. I. V'yunov for discussing results and quality-made figure 2.

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